

Exchange rates and expenditure of households with foreign-born members: Evidence from Australia

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Key findings

- The 2014-2015 depreciation of the Australian dollar caused Australian households with foreign-born members (HFBMs) to increase their food and overall expenditure, compared to their native counterparts.
- A one percent depreciation in the exchange rate of the host country (Australia) currency increases migrant households' food and total expenditure in the host country by 0.12 per cent.

What we knew

- Exchange rates can affect the inflow or outflow of foreign remittances (Faini; 1994; Yang; 2008).
- For example, the sudden decline in the exchange rate of the Filipino Peso during the 1997 Asian financial crisis resulted in increased international remittances to the Philippines (Yang; 2008).
- The effect of exchange rates on remittances can thus affect the macroeconomy in recipient countries, as well as individuals.
- Little attention has been given to how movements in exchange rates can affect immigrants differently than natives in the host country.

What we do

- We examine whether currency depreciation affects the expenditure of households with foreign-born members (HFBM), which we use as a proxy for immigrant families, differently than natives.
- Specifically, we investigate the change in HFBMs' food and total expenditures, compared to natives, that results from a large depreciation of the Australian dollar during 2014-15.
- This question is akin to asking whether remittances are a substitute or a complement good for migrants relative to consumption in the host country.
- Using a difference-in-differences methodology and the 2013–2015 Nielson Homescan Panel Survey data, we find that HFBMs spent more on food in 2014 and 2015 compared to their native counterparts.
- Using the Household Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) survey, we verify our results for food and verify a similar result for total expenditure.

What we know now

- Exchange rate changes affect immigrants' expenditure differently than natives. We rule out alternative explanations for our results, such as differences between immigrants and natives in consumption of imports, income growth and price changes.
- Our findings are consistent with reduced spending by immigrants both in terms of remittances and in terms of travelling back to their countries of origin.

What this means for policy

- Expenditure and consumption can be poor measures of welfare for migrant households when compared to native households. Depreciation of the host country's currency unambiguously lowers migrant households' welfare by reducing real incomes. Higher consumption/expenditure relative to their native counterparts may nonetheless occur, providing a misleading picture of migrant households' welfare.
- Countries receiving large remittances need to be aware of the potential impacts on those remittances of exchange rate fluctuations. Inasmuch as those countries rely on exchange rate remittances for investment or social welfare, they might consider policies to offset the impact of reduced remittances.

Where to now

- Research focusing on immigrant households' expenditure patterns, including their remitting behavior, may provide more direct evidence of the impact of exchange rate changes on well-being. Adding remittance-related questions to HILDA and other household income/expenditure surveys in Australia would aid in conducting such research.
- Our results are likely driven by the behavior of permanent migrants. Temporary migrants, constrained by their financial situation and with an expectation of a short stay in the host country, may not change their remitting behavior. Again, better data and more research is required to make conclusions about this group.

More information

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- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au or s.a.hasan@massey.ac.nz

References

- Faini, R. (1994). Workers remittances and the real exchange rate, *Journal of Population Economics* **7**(2): 235–245.
- Yang, D. (2008). International migration, remittances and household investment: evidence from Philippine migrants' exchange rate shocks, *The Economic Journal* **118**(528): 591–630.